

NUMERICAL APPLICATIONS AND VERIFICATION OF AN INTEGRATED FLOW-STRESS MODEL IN PROCESSING OF THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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Abstract

This paper presents numerical examples to study both aspects of flow-compaction and stress development throughout the curing process of thermoset composite materials and the effects of resin flow on the development of residual stresses predicted by a newly developed integrated model. Various numerical examples ranging from simplified cases represented by a single finite element to unidirectional composite laminates undergoing autoclave curing process are considered. To verify the integrated model, the results obtained from these numerical examples are compared to those generated from established individual models for stress development in the composite material. The numerical examples will also serve to provide comparisons for predictions of stress development over the domain of the processed composite laminate with those obtained by regular stress models that consider either the initial or final resin volume fractions.

Introduction

The behaviour of thermoset matrix composites undergoing cure may be divided into two distinct stages: pre-gelation and post-gelation. During the first stage, flow of resin through the fibre-bed plays a major role in deformation of the part as the viscosity of the uncured resin drops significantly due to the increase in temperature. During the post-gelation phase, the gelled resin and the fibres deform as a whole, leading to the expected solid composite material response.

In current process models, each of these two aspects is dealt with using separate sub-models, typically called the flow and stress modules. The flow module is relevant to the pre-gelation behaviour of resin,

while the stress module is valid for the post-gelation of composite material. Typically in process simulations, the flow module is run from the start of the process until resin is gelled throughout the composite laminate. Then the geometry and volume fractions are updated and re-meshing is performed if deemed necessary. The last step involves running the stress module with the new properties from the beginning to the end of the process. Therefore, only the effect of resin flow on the final geometry and properties of the composite material is considered in the prediction of residual stresses and the ongoing influence of flow on the development of stresses in the composite system is overlooked.

In a previous work by the authors [1] the basic framework for the integration of modeling porous flow of resin through the fibre bed with the simulation of stress development in the composite material during the processing cycle was presented in a unified model. Such a unified model capable of capturing both aspects of flow and stress development in an integrated manner enables one to seamlessly track and analyse the resin flow, deformation, and stress development in the composite throughout the curing process.

Governing Equations

The integrated modelling approach used in this work is developed based on a 2-D plane strain flow-compaction FE representation. The governing equations for flow and deformation of porous media involve three distinct equations including the equilibrium equation of the fluid phase, the equilibrium equation of the two-phase system, and the mass conservation equation. The two-phase model is modified so that it can capture both the stress development and resin flow. These include,

but are not limited to, modifications to the mass conservation equation to produce bulk elastic properties consistent with the stress models for cured composites; introduction of a modified concept of effective stress; and modifications to the numerical solution technique.

Incorporating the above modifications in the governing equations of general two-phase media leads to [1]

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u}_{i,i} + v_{i,i} - \dot{\epsilon}_{v_s} = 0 \\ -\phi P_{,i} - f_{di} = 0 \\ \sigma_{s-pij,j} - bP_{,i} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

as the set of governing equations for the integrated model. The three equations in (1) are the mass conservation equation, the equilibrium equation of the resin matrix, and the total equilibrium equation, respectively. In deriving (1), the effect of body forces is neglected. u , v , and P are the main variables of the above differential equations. u is the displacement of the solid structure which is representative of the displacement field of the system, v is the relative velocity field of resin, while P represents the resin pressure. $\dot{\epsilon}_{v_s}$ is the rate of volumetric strain of the two-phase system, and is defined by

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{v_s} = \frac{1}{K_c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{tr \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s}{\delta_{ii}} \right) \quad (2)$$

so that the bulk behaviour of the two-phase system is consistent with the micromechanics formulation of choice for the moduli of the cured composite. $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s$ is the total stress of the two-phase system, and K_c is the bulk modulus of the system obtained from the relevant micromechanics formulation. ϕ denotes the volume fraction of resin, and b is the Biot coefficient [2] defined by

$$b = 1 - \frac{K_{fb}}{K_f} \quad (3)$$

where K_{fb} is the bulk modulus of the fibre-bed (solid skeleton in general) and K_f is the bulk modulus of individual fibres (solid grains in general). f_{di} are the components of the drag force between the solid and fluid phases that, if defined as follows

$$f_{di} = -\phi \mu S_{ij}^{-1} v_j \quad (4)$$

lead to the Darcy's law [3]. μ is the viscosity of the fluid phase, and S is the permeability matrix of the porous fibre-bed. σ_{s-pij} are the components of the 'modified fibre-bed' stress tensor. For isotropic materials, the elastic moduli that relate the modified fibre-bed stress tensor to the strain field are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} K_{s-p} &= K_{fb}, \\ G_{s-p} &= G_{fb} + G_c \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where G_{fb} is the shear modulus of fibre-bed, and G_c is the shear modulus of the composite material obtained from the selected micromechanics scheme. For brevity, the formulation of the integrated approach for transversely isotropic materials is not discussed in this paper. More theoretical details of the integrated approach may be found in Haghshenas et al. [1] and Haghshenas [4]. The integrated formulation is introduced into a Q₁P₀ bilinear isoparametric element with 4 nodes for the system displacement and relative velocity of the fluid phase, and only one central node assigned to pressure of the fluid phase. This element, which is depicted schematically in Fig. 1, will also be referred to as the 4-1 element. The stress development model used in this work is based on a pseudo-viscoelastic model presented by Zobeiry et al. [5].

Numerical Applications

The integrated model was implemented in a MATLAB code developed in-house. The stress model based on the pseudo-viscoelastic formulation was also separately implemented in MATLAB to compare its results with those reported by the integrated approach. The finite element chosen for the stress model is a 4-noded bilinear isoparametric element in 2D plane strain. Clearly in this case the

DOFs are only of the displacement type. In terms of discretizing the displacement field this element is essentially identical to the 4-1 element.

The composite material in all of the examples considered in this work is assumed to be AS4/3501-6. The material properties pertaining to the flow-compaction behaviour of AS4/3501-6 are adapted from Hubert et al. [6]. The thermo-mechanical properties of the fibres and resin are presented in Table 1. We assume that both the shear and bulk moduli, G , and K , of the resin evolve with changes in temperature and degree of cure throughout the processing. CTE_g and CTE_r are resin's glassy and rubbery coefficients of thermal expansion, respectively. CSC is the volumetric cure shrinkage coefficient of resin. The relaxation times and their associated weight factors for 3501-6 resin are obtained from Kim and White [7]. Subscripts u and r denote the un-relaxed and relaxed values of the moduli respectively.

Example 1. Fully constrained unidirectional [0°] laminate

In this example, the stress development in a fully constrained composite material undergoing cure is studied. The sample is assumed to be a unidirectional [0°] laminate with a length of 1 mm and a height of 4 mm (Fig. 2). The problem is modeled by a single 4-1 element and the time-step size chosen for the numerical solution is 30 seconds. All boundaries are assumed to be impermeable, and since all the kinematic DOFs are located on the boundary of the single element, resin flow is completely inhibited. The temperature history and the resulting change in the degree of cure and viscosity of resin are presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. Fig. 5 depicts the time-history of σ_x using the integrated model and compares the results with those obtained from the stress model. Fig. 6 presents the comparison of the through-thickness or transverse stress, σ_z with the results obtained from the stress model. It can be seen that predictions from both models are virtually identical.

Example 2. Uni-axially constrained [0°] laminate under pressure loading applied on the permeable boundary

In this example, the stress development response of a uni-axially constrained composite material

undergoing cure is studied. The geometry and B.C. of the problem are presented in Fig. 7 where the applied pressure on the top surface is $f_0=540$ kPa. The sample is a unidirectional [0°] laminate with an assumed width of 1 mm and a height of 4 mm. The top surface of the sample is assumed to be permeable. The temperature history and the resulting degree of cure and viscosity of resin are the same as the previous examples in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. The problem is modeled by a single 4-1 element.

Fig. 8 presents the time-history of the developed resin pressure in the system. Fig. 9 depicts the changes in the vertical velocity of resin at the top surface of the sample during the process. The evolution of the resin volume fraction, ϕ , obtained by the integrated model is presented in Fig. 10. The predictions of the stress model with initial and final volume fractions are superimposed for comparison. Note that the final volume fractions are obtained from the integrated model. The changes in the transverse strain of the system are presented in Fig. 11 and compared with the results of the stress model assuming both initial and final volume fractions. At the early stages of the process, the resin undergoes expansion due to temperature rise and, in the presence of a permeable boundary, resin flows out of the system to relieve some of the developed pressure. In the first few minutes however, an insignificant amount of resin flows out of the system as at that stage not enough pressure has built up in the resin. This is evident in the initial agreement between the predictions of transverse strain in the sample obtained by the integrated model and the stress model. Fig. 12 depicts the time-history of the stress along the x-axis, and compares the results with those obtained by the stress model assuming both initial and final volume fractions.

The applied pressure provides a significant motivation for the resin flow and leads to a maximum resin velocity that is one order of magnitude larger than that in the previous example. The large amount of resin flow, leads to an appreciable difference between the initial and final values of resin volume fraction. This causes the trend of the post-gelation behaviour of the system obtained by the integrated model to be different from the one predicted by the stress model based on the initial volume fractions. Fig. 12 clearly shows the difference between the stress predictions of the

integrated model and the results obtained from the stress models based on the initial and final volume fractions.

The flow of resin is responsible for the insignificant amount of longitudinal stress predicted by the integrated approach while the stress models predict significant stresses in the x-direction. After the gelation of resin, the stress time-history predicted by the integrated model essentially becomes an offset of the predictions of the stress model with final volume fraction.

Example 3. Flat unidirectional laminate undergoing cure

Here, we consider a flat unidirectional laminate fully bonded to a rigid tool. All material properties remain the same as in the previous two examples. The geometry and BC of the problem are depicted in Fig. 13. Due to symmetry, only half of the length of the laminate is analysed. Fig. 14 shows the autoclave temperature cycle. It also presents the assumed thermal history of the part and the resulting degree of cure of resin throughout the processing. The predictions obtained using three approaches will be analysed and compared here: (i) the integrated model, (ii) the stress model using initial distribution of resin volume fraction, and (iii) the stress model using the final distribution of resin volume fraction. We investigate three different directions for the placement of the fibres: $[0^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$. The applied load on the top and side surfaces of the sample is 540 kPa. The problem is modeled by 12×6 , 16×8 , and 20×16 meshes of 4-1 elements to ensure the convergence of results. Time-step sizes of 60, 12, and 6 seconds are used and the convergence of results with refining the time-steps was confirmed. The 20×16 mesh and time-step size of 6 seconds are chosen to report the results and comparisons.

To verify the stresses predicted by the stress model, the beta version of the commercially available COMPRO CCA in ABAQUS was used [8] incorporating the variable time pseudo-viscoelastic (PVE) formulation of Zobeiry et al. [3]. A 3D equivalent of our 2D plane strain was modeled using a mesh of 20×16 elements for $[0^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$ lay-ups. Fig. 15 shows the comparison of profiles of σ_x at section AB for $[0^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$ lay-ups. It can be seen that the stress results of the MATLAB plane strain and ABAQUS 3D models compare very well.

Fig. 16 shows the through-thickness profile of σ_x at section AB of the $[0^\circ]$ laminate obtained by the three approaches. It is observed that the two stress model approaches lead to a rather large change in the amount of developed stress in the x direction in the neighbourhood of the constrained boundary AE. These sudden changes are accompanied by some oscillations that die down quite rapidly as we move away from the constrained boundary. The sudden development of stress in the vicinity of the boundary occurs because the constraint on the bottom surface effectively constrains the fibres located at the bottom of the laminate from any movement in the x direction. This combined with the thermal expansion of resin prior to gelation leads to significant development of stress in that region. The response obtained from the integrated model (solid line) is different in that this boundary layer effect is not observed. The predictions of the stress model with the final volume fractions agrees very well with the one obtained from the integrated model as we move away from the constrained boundary. This shows that the difference between the two results (which is located in the vicinity of the constrained bottom surface) is in fact due to stresses that are predicted by the stress model to develop before the nominal gelation of resin while in the integrated model no such stresses develop since the excess amount of resin can flow out of the system as it undergoes thermal expansion. In the case of $[90^\circ]$ layup, as it was observed earlier in Fig. 15, there are no signs of sudden changes in σ_x predicted by stress models since the fibre direction is transverse to the x-axis.

Fig. 17 and Fig. 18 present the final distribution of axial forces and bending moments, respectively, along the length of the laminate. As a general rule, the results predicted by the stress model with final volume fractions are closer to those predicted by the integrated model than the regular stress model approach based on initial volume fraction. This is especially more noticeable in the axial force diagrams. This difference could be attributed to the flow of resin through and out of the system in the integrated approach. Note that there is a sudden change observed in the distribution of axial forces and moments in a region close to the side EF of the laminate. These anomalies, which are clearly visible in Fig. 18, are the artifacts of the inherent singularity

at point E where the assumed fully constrained BC at the bottom meets the free BC on the side EF.

Conclusion

Various numerical examples ranging from simplified 1D cases represented by a single finite element to a more complex flat composite laminate undergoing cure were presented and analyzed using the integrated flow-stress model. The results obtained for these numerical examples were used to verify the predictions of the integrated model as compared to established individual models for stress development in the composite material. The numerical examples also served to provide comparisons of stress development in the processed composite laminate with those obtained by regular stress models considering both initial and final resin volume fractions.

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Fig. 1. Schematic representation of Q_1P_0 (4-1) linear isoparametric element

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of a fully constrained $[0^\circ]$ composite sample (Example 1)

Table 1. Mechanical properties of AS4/3501-6

Property	AS4 fibre	Property	3501-6 resin
V_{12}	0.2	K^u (GPa)	3.556
V_{23}	0.3	K^r (GPa)	0.8
E_1 (GPa)	207	G^u (GPa)	1.185
E_2 (GPa)	20.7	G^r (kPa)	1
G_{12} (GPa)	27.6	CTE_g ($^{\circ}C$)	5.76×10^{-5}
CTE_1 ($^{\circ}C$)	-0.9×10^{-6}	CTE_r ($^{\circ}C$)	1.854×10^{-4}
CTE_2 ($^{\circ}C$)	7.2×10^{-6}	CSC (vol.c)	-0.05488

Fig. 3. Time-history of the applied temperature and the resulting degree of cure in Examples 1 and 2

Fig. 4. Time-history of the applied temperature and the resulting resin viscosity in Examples 1 and 2

Fig. 5. Time-history of the development of longitudinal stress in Example 1 predicted by the integrated and stress models. The predictions are essentially identical.

Fig. 6. Time-history of the development of transverse stress in Example 1 predicted by the integrated and stress models. The predictions are essentially identical.

Fig. 7. Schematic representation of a uni-axially constrained $[0^\circ]$ composite laminate, with permeable BC and pressure loading on the top surface (Example 2)

Fig. 8. Time-history of the development of resin pressure in Example 2

Fig. 9. Time-history of the changes in resin velocity in the vertical direction at the top surface of Example 2

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Fig. 10. Time-history of the changes in resin volume fraction in Example 2

Fig. 11. Time-history of the transverse strain in Example 2

Fig. 12. Time-history of the development of σ_x in Example 2

Fig. 13. Geometry and BC of the flat composite laminate undergoing cure (Example 3)

Fig. 14. Time-history of the autoclave and part temperatures and the resulting degree of cure in Example 3

Fig. 15. Final profiles of σ_x predicted by the stress model at section AB of the $[0^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$ flat laminates, and their comparison with the corresponding predictions using 3D elements in ABAQUS

Fig. 16. Final profile of σ_x at section AB of the $[0^\circ]$ flat laminate

Fig. 17. Final distribution of axial force along the length of the $[0^\circ]$ flat laminate

Fig. 18. Final distribution of bending moment along the length of the $[0^\circ]$ flat laminate

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